

phosphoinositide-3-kinase regulatory subunit 1 (PIK3R1) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : Phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3Ks) are a family of intracellular signal transducer enzymes that phosphorylate the 3-prime hydroxyl group of the inositol ring of phosphatidylinositol (PtdIns). PIK3R1 is a subunit of PI3K. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of PIK3R1, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: PIK3R1, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

*ML dicoveries of PIK3R1 synergy in Meningiomas

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossil, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecortius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinghieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. phosphoinositide-3-kinase regulatory subunit 1 (PIK3R1)

Reversible phosphorylation of inositol lipids controls various functions in cells. Studies in the 1980s established that activated growth factor receptors and oncoproteins associated with an enzyme that phosphorylates PtdIns.

Sugimoto et al. [13] investigated the ability of purified Rous sarcoma virus transforming gene product ($pp60^{v-src}$), to phosphorylate phosphatidylinositol and diacylglycerol. They observed that Phosphatidylinositol was phosphorylated to form both mono- and diphosphorylated derivatives and 1,2-Diacylglycerol was phosphorylated to form phosphatidic acid, which pointed to the same thermolability and the same sensitivity to inhibitors as shown by the casein kinase activity of $pp60^{v-src}$.

Polyoma middle-T antigen is required for viral transformation of cultured cells and for tumorigenesis in animals. middle-T is bound to the membrane and has an asso-

ciated tyrosine kinase activity which seems to result from the interaction of middle-T with pp60^{c-src}, the cellular homologue of pp60^{v-src}. pp60^{v-src} was shown to have an associated phosphatidylinositol (PI) kinase activity in vitro and to increase PI turnover in vivo. Whitman et al. [14] assayed for PI kinase activity in immunoprecipitates made with middle-T- or pp60^{c-src}- specific antisera of cells infected with polyoma virus. They detected a PI kinase activity in those immunoprecipitates which contained middle-T. Studies of mutants of middle-T defective in transformation have showed a close correlation between PI kinase activity and transformation.

At this time, only two phosphoinositides were known to exist - • phosphatidylinositol-4-phosphate (PtdIns-4-P) and • phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate (PtdIns-4,5-P₂). These findings led to the proposal that phosphoinositide 3-kinase (PI3K) activity was important for cellular responses to growth factors and for malignant transformation. Herman and Emr [15] cloned the first PI3K gene *S. cerevisiae* VPS34, which was required for vacuolar protein sorting in yeast and is the only PI3K gene in that organism. VPS34 gene function is required for the efficient localization of a variety of vacuolar proteins and they sequenced the wild-type VPS34 gene in order to gain a better understanding of the role of its protein product in this intracellular sorting pathway.

Szulzewsky et al. [12] The PI3K intracellular pathway regulates cell growth, motility, and survival and transmits signals from several receptor types, including RTKs, G protein-coupled receptors, and small Ras-related GTPases. Upon receptor activation, the plasma membrane-associated lipid kinase PI3K is recruited to the receptor and catalyzes the phosphorylation of phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate (PIP₂) to produce phosphatidylinositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate (PIP₃), a second messenger inositol that binds to the pleckstrin homology (PH) domain of the serine/threonine kinase AKT, thereby localizing AKT and its upstream activating kinase PDK-1 to the cell membrane. Phosphorylation of AKT at Thr308 by PDK-1 and subsequent phosphorylation at Ser473 by mTORC2 leads to its full activation and this activated AKT then phosphorylates many substrates involved in cell proliferation, metabolism, survival, and motility. Fruman et al. [16] provide a detailed review on the roles of class I PI3Ks in the regulation of cellular metabolism and in immune system functions, areas which are closely intertwined with cancer biology.

PI3K consists of three subunits, namely - • the p110 α catalytic subunit encoded by PIK3R1, • the p85 α regulatory subunit encoded by PIK3R1 and • p55 regulatory subunit.

Otsu et al. [17] characterized two 85 kd proteins that associate with receptor tyrosine kinases, middle-T/pp60^{c-src} complexes, and PI3-kinase. They observed that affinity-purified bovine brain phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3-kinase) contained two major proteins of 85 and 110 kd, while their amino acid sequence analysis and cDNA cloning revealed two related 85 kd proteins (p85 α and p85 β), which both contained one SH3 and two SH2 regions (src homology regions). Further, they observed that when expressed, these 85 kd proteins bound to and were substrates for tyrosine-phosphorylated receptor kinases and the polyoma virus middle-T antigen/pp60^{c-src} complex, but lack PI3-kinase activity. It was also seen that the active PI3-kinase complex containing p85 α or p85 β and the 110 kd protein binds to PDGF but not EGF receptors. Thus, they hypothesized that p85 α and p85 β may mediate specific PI3-kinase interactions with a subset of tyrosine kinases.

Oestrogen is known to produce diverse biological effects through binding to the oestrogen receptor (ER). The ER is a steroid hormone nuclear receptor, which, when bound to oestrogen, modulates the transcriptional activity of target genes. Simoncini et al. [18] showed that the ER isoform, ER α , bound in a ligand-dependent manner to the p85 α regulatory subunit of phosphatidylinositol-3-OH kinase (PI3K). Their stimulation with oestrogen increased ER α -associated PI3K activity, leading to the activation of protein kinase B/AKT and endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS). Further, recruitment and activation of PI3K by ligand-bound ER α were independent of gene transcription, did not involve phosphotyrosine adapter molecules or src-homology domains of p85 α , and extended to other steroid hormone receptors. They showed that this vascular protective effect of oestrogen was abolished in the presence of PI3K or eNOS inhibitors. Their findings defined a physiologically important non-nuclear oestrogen-signalling pathway involving the direct interaction of ER α with PI3K.

Ueki et al. [19] used fibroblastic cell lines derived from PIK3R1 gene KO embryos to elucidate the functions of the regulatory subunits of Class Ia phosphoinositide (PI) 3-kinase in insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF1) signaling and the molecular mechanisms of these complicated phenotypes in the KO mice. (PI) 3-kinase is comprised of a p110 catalytic subunit and a regulatory subunit, the most common family of which is derived from the p85 α gene (PIK3R1). They found that normal cells exhibited an imbalance between the catalytic and regulatory subunits of PI 3-kinase and that modification of the molecular balance between the subunits of PI 3-kinase could play a major role in insulin/IGF-1 signaling, cellular metabolism, and cell survival. In wild-type cells, the p85 subunit was more abundant than p110, leading to competition between the p85 monomer and the p85-p110 dimer and ineffective signaling. Their heterozygous disruption of PIK3R1 resulted in increased AKT activity and decreased apoptosis by IGF1 through up-regulated phosphatidylinositol (3,4,5)-triphosphate production. Complete depletion of p85 α , on the other hand, resulted in significantly increased apoptosis due to reduced PI 3-kinase-dependent signaling. Thus, a reduction in p85 α signified a novel therapeutic target for enhancing IGF1/insulin signaling, prolongation of cell survival, and protection against apoptosis.

It is known that several human cancers involve up-regulation of the phosphoinositide 3-kinase PI3K α , with oncogenic mutations in both the p110 α catalytic and the p85 α regulatory subunits. Miled et al. [20] used crystallographic and biochemical approaches to gain insight into activating mutations in two noncatalytic p110 α domains—the adaptor-binding and the helical domains. They observed that a structure of the adaptor-binding domain of p110 α in a complex with the p85 α inter-Src homology 2 (inter-SH2) domain showed that oncogenic mutations in the adaptor-binding domain are not at the inter-SH2 interface but in a polar surface patch that is a plausible docking site for other domains in the holo p110/p85 complex. They also examined helical domain mutations and found that the Glu⁵⁴⁵ to Lys⁵⁴⁵ (E545K) oncogenic mutant disrupted an inhibitory charge-charge interaction with the p85 N-terminal SH2 domain. Their studies extend the understanding of the architecture of PI3Ks and provided a view into how the two classes of mutations that cause a gain in function could lead to cancer. SMO and AKT1 mutations are very common in meningiomas and has raised the possibility of targeted therapies for some patients. Using high-resolution array-comparative genomic hybridization, Abedalthagafi et al. [21] characterized copy-number changes in

150 meningiomas and then characterized these samples for mutations in AKT1, KLF4, NF2, PIK3CA, SMO, and TRAF7. Similar to prior reports, they identified AKT1 and SMO mutations in a subset of non-NF2-mutant meningiomas (ie, 9% and 6%, respectively) and detected oncogenic mutations in PIK3CA in 7% of non-NF2-mutant meningiomas. They observed that AKT1, KLF4, and PIK3CA mutations often co-occurred with mutations in TRAF7. Further, they report that PIK3CA-mutant meningiomas showed limited chromosomal instability and were enriched in the skull base thus leading to the conclusion that PI3K signaling is an important target for precision medicine trials in meningioma patients.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [22] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2nd order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [23] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, •

linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [23].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [24]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [25], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance

based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [22] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [22]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [26], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the

projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. PIK3R1 related synergies

Note - PIK3R1 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 ^{2nd} order combinations of PIK3R1 were recorded.

3.1.1. PIK3R1 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with PIK3R1 showed high rankings -
semaphorin 3F (SEMA3F), CD38 molecule (CD38), CD4 molecule (CD4), arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase (ALOX5), CD74 molecule (CD74), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family A member 2 (APBA2), collagen type XI alpha 1 chain (COL11A1), PR/SET domain 6 (PRDM6), tetraspanin 32 (TSPAN32), integrin subunit beta 5 (ITGB5), solute carrier family 23 member 2 (SLC23A2), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 5 (PCSK5), nuclear factor of activated T cells 4 (NFATC4), CD40 molecule (CD40), regulating synaptic membrane exocytosis 4 (RIMS4), matrix remodeling associated 5 (MXRA5), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 1 inhibitor (PCSK1N), C-C motif chemokine ligand 22 (CCL22), coronin 2B (CORO2B), platelet derived growth factor receptor like (PDGFRL), procollagen C-endopeptidase enhancer (PCOLCE), endoglin (ENG), cadherin related 23 (CDH23), cholinergic receptor nicotinic epsilon subunit (CHRNE), contactin associated protein 1 (CNTNAP1), collagen type I alpha 1 chain (COL1A1), peripheral myelin protein 22 (PMP22), tripartite motif containing 2 (TRIM2), crystallin alpha B (CRYAB), solute carrier family 35 member F2 (SLC35F2), SAM and SH3 domain containing 1 (SASH1), vanin 1 (VNN1), growth hormone re-

ceptor (GHR), chromodomain helicase DNA binding protein 6 (CDH6), par-3 family cell polarity regulator beta (PARD3B), Wnt ligand secretion mediator (WLS), olfactomedin like 3 (OLFML3), immunoglobulin superfamily member 21 (IGSF21), patched 2 (PTCH2), neuropilin 2 (NRP2), chromosome 1 open reading frame 198 (C1orf198), PHD finger protein 19 (PHF19), plexin domain containing 2 (PLXDC2), cysteine rich secretory protein LCCL domain containing 1 (CRISPLD1), plasminogen activator, urokinase (PLAU), basic helix-loop-helix family member e41 (BHLHE41), sarcoglycan epsilon (SGCE), FCH and mu domain containing endocytic adaptor 1 (FCHO1), peroxidase (PXDN), leukocyte immunoglobulin like receptor B2 (LILRB2), myosin heavy chain 10 (MYH10), leucine rich repeats and calponin homology domain containing 1 (LRCH1), lymphocyte cytosolic protein 1 (LCP1), alpha kinase 3 (ALPK3), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 2 (ENPP2), synaptotagmin like 2 (SYTL2), elastin microfibril interfacier 1 (EMILIN1), cerebellin 3 precursor (CBLN3), fibulin 5 (FBLN5), insulin like growth factor binding protein 4 (IGFBP4), NLR family pyrin domain containing 12 (NLRP12), chromosome 1 open reading frame 162 (C1orf162), RNA binding motif single stranded interacting protein 3 (RBMS3), golgi associated kinase 1A (GASK1A / FAM198A), CTD small phosphatase like (CTD-SPL), myosin heavy chain 15 (MYH15), BOC cell adhesion associated, oncogene regulated (BOC), OTU deubiquitinase with linear linkage specificity like (OTULINL / FAM105A), spermatogenesis associated 9 (SPATA9), tripartite motif containing 7 (TRIM7), dishevelled associated activator of morphogenesis 2 (DAAM2), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 3 subunit (CHRN3), neurotrophic receptor tyrosine kinase 2 (NTRK2), dopamine receptor D2 (DRD2), fasciculation and elongation protein zeta 1 (FEZ1), mohawk homeobox (MKX), serine protease 23 (PRSS23), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 6 (KCNA6), ADAM metallopeptidase with thrombospondin type 1 motif 12 (ADAMTS12), phosphotyrosine interaction domain containing 1 (PID1), ABI family member 3 binding protein (ABI3BP), phosphodiesterase 1C (PDE1C), matrix metallopeptidase 16 (MMP16), tetraspanin 7 (TSPAN7), protein phosphatase 2 regulatory subunit Bbeta (PPP2R2B), exostosin like glycosyltransferase 1 (EXTL1), S100 calcium binding protein B (S100B), collagen type XXVI alpha 1 chain (COL26A1), vascular cell adhesion molecule 1 (VCAM1), frizzled related protein (FRZB), coiled-coil domain containing 74A (CCDC74A), C1q and TNF related 7 (C1QTNF7), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family B member 2 (APBB2), 15-hydroxyprostaglandin dehydrogenase (HPGD), coagulation factor II thrombin receptor like 2 (F2RL2), Rho related BTB domain containing 3 (RHOBTB3), EBF transcription factor 1 (EBF1), transmembrane protein 200A (TMEM200A), myozenin 3 (MYOZ3), somatomedin B and thrombospondin type 1 domain containing (SBSPON), carbonic anhydrase 3 (CA3), sushi, von Willebrand factor type A, EGF and pentraxin domain containing 1 (SVEP1), heat shock protein family A (Hsp70) member 12A (HSPA12A), PDZ domain containing ring finger 4 (PDZRN4), transmembrane protein 130 (TMEM130), nicotinamide N-methyltransferase (NNMT), proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2), vesicle associated membrane protein 5 (VAMP5), energy homeostasis associated (ENHO), carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1C (CPT1C), serine/threonine kinase 32A (STK32A), secretogranin II (SCG2), StAR related lipid transfer domain containing 5 (STARD5), pseudopodium enriched atypical kinase 1 (PEAK1), sushi domain containing 5 (SUSD5), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), CD248 molecule

(CD248), dynein axonemal heavy chain 12 (DNAH12), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 3A1 (SLCO3A1), BCL2 family apoptosis regulator BOK (BOK), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), serine rich and transmembrane domain containing 1 (SERTM1), phospholipase C beta 1 (PLCB1), neurotrimin (NTM), regulator of G protein signaling 6 (RGS6), pappalysin 1 (PAPPA), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A5, pseudogene (ANKRD20A5P), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), family with sequence similarity 180 member A (FAM180A), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), family with sequence similarity 180 member B (FAM180B), sialophorin (SPN), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), matrix metalloproteinase 17 (MMP17), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), NALCN channel auxiliary factor 1 (NALF1 / FAM155A), vitrin (VIT), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of PIK3R1 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t PIK3R1 with PIK3R1 – > SEMA3F / CD38 / CD4 / ALOX5 / CD74 / APBA2 / COL11A1 / PRDM6 / TSPAN32 / ITGB5 / SLC23A2 / PCSK5 / NFATC4 / CD40 / RIMS4 / MXRA5 / PCSK1N / CCL22 / CORO2B / PDGFRL / PCOLCE / ENG / CDH23 / CHRNE / CNTNAP1 / COL1A1 / PMP22 / TRIM2 / CRYAB / SLC35F2 / SASH1 / VNN1 / GHR / CDH6 / PARD3B / WLS / OLFML3 / IGSF21 / PTCH2 / NRP2 / C1orf198 / PHF19 / PLXDC2 / CRISPLD1 / PLAU / BHLHE41 / SGCE / FCHO1 / PXDN / LILRB2 / MYH10 / LRCH1 / LCP1 / ALPK3 / ENPP2 / SYTL2 / EMILIN1 / CBLN3 / FBLN5 / IGFBP4 / NLRP12 / C1orf162 / RBMS3 / FAM198A / CTDSPL / MYH15 / BOC / FAM105A / SPATA9 / TRIM7 / DAAM2 / CHRNB3 / NTRK2 / DRD2 / FEZ1 / MKX / PRSS23 / KCNA6 / ADAMTS12 / PID1 / ABI3BP / PDE1C / MMP16 / TSPAN7 / PPP2R2B / EXTL1 / S100B / COL26A1 / VCAM1 / FRZB / CCDC74A / C1QTNF7 / APBB2 / HPGD / F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 / EBF1 / TMEM200A / MYOZ3 / SBSPON / CA3 / SVEP1 / HSPA12A / PDZRN4 / TMEM130 / NNMT / PRRT2 / VAMP5 / ENHO / CPT1C / STK32A / SCG2 / STARD5 / PEAK1 / SUSD5 / HOXB2 / CD248 / DNAH12 /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS PIK3R1									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T PIK3R1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
SEMA3F - PIK3R1	122	268	159	367	CD38 - PIK3R1	276	321	263	230
CD4 - PIK3R1	343	241	324	174	ALOX5 - PIK3R1	272	178	120	349
CD74 - PIK3R1	374	345	338	283	APBA2 - PIK3R1	299	342	272	304
COL11A1 - PIK3R1	231	361	327	301	PRDM6 - PIK3R1	310	208	330	352
TSPAN32 - PIK3R1	298	225	290	267	ITGB5 - PIK3R1	333	319	225	265
SLC23A2 - PIK3R1	328	192	347	291	PCSK5 - PIK3R1	367	245	193	143
NFATC4 - PIK3R1	224	263	222	326	CD40 - PIK3R1	307	207	142	171
RIMS4 - PIK3R1	293	355	201	343	MXRA5 - PIK3R1	287	227	247	369
PCSK1N - PIK3R1	233	283	86	233	CCL22 - PIK3R1	283	138	268	353
CORO2B - PIK3R1	255	55	185	372	PDGFRL - PIK3R1	223	346	113	157
PCOLCE - PIK3R1	349	363	292	151	ENG - PIK3R1	290	232	220	358
CDH23 - PIK3R1	309	141	206	192	CHRNE - PIK3R1	282	299	326	38
CNTNAP1 - PIK3R1	296	248	249	322	COL1A1 - PIK3R1	219	191	188	359
PMP22 - PIK3R1	219	191	188	359	TRIM2 - PIK3R1	361	195	157	312
CRYAB - PIK3R1	273	293	257	100	SLC35F2 - PIK3R1	335	233	203	384
SASH1 - PIK3R1	167	229	312	324	VNN1 - PIK3R1	372	295	281	133
GHR - PIK3R1	228	222	199	357	CDH6 - PIK3R1	74	242	258	321
PARD3B - PIK3R1	253	282	149	270	WLS - PIK3R1	266	205	209	275
OLFML3 - PIK3R1	243	26	181	389	IGSF21 - PIK3R1	221	238	208	123
PTCH2 - PIK3R1	305	186	237	375	NRP2 - PIK3R1	337	145	300	314
C1orf198 - PIK3R1	373	296	291	109	PHF19 - PIK3R1	251	206	255	70
PLXDC2 - PIK3R1	248	354	318	278	CRISPLD1 - PIK3R1	356	198	200	287
PLAU - PIK3R1	203	173	182	339	BHLHE41 - PIK3R1	226	327	248	363
SGCE - PIK3R1	64	281	186	262	FCHO1 - PIK3R1	281	334	345	336
PXDN - PIK3R1	291	301	106	373	LILRB2 - PIK3R1	308	356	214	309
MYH10 - PIK3R1	317	312	274	274	LRCH1 - PIK3R1	246	122	339	325
LCPI - PIK3R1	323	278	306	196	ALPK3 - PIK3R1	267	276	353	261
ENPP2 - PIK3R1	192	269	287	137	SYTL2 - PIK3R1	326	69	262	381
EMILIN1 - PIK3R1	244	254	298	93	CBLN3 - PIK3R1	354	216	176	334
FBLN5 - PIK3R1	101	339	296	297	IGFBP4 - PIK3R1	386	120	322	252
NLRP12 - PIK3R1	269	359	304	327	C1orf162 - PIK3R1	347	309	331	255
RBMS3 - PIK3R1	263	328	251	161	FAM198A - PIK3R1	254	228	342	247
CTDSPL - PIK3R1	300	298	294	310	MYH15 - PIK3R1	189	291	246	379
BOC - PIK3R1	292	240	197	48	FAM105A - PIK3R1	320	308	308	351
SPATA9 - PIK3R1	278	176	314	95	TRIM7 - PIK3R1	50	358	334	378
DAAM2 - PIK3R1	268	233	364	193	CHRN3 - PIK3R1	377	383	375	152
NTRK2 - PIK3R1	327	273	383	232	DRD2 - PIK3R1	387	364	381	183
FEZ1 - PIK3R1	330	352	267	300	MKX - PIK3R1	207	366	321	296
PRSS23 - PIK3R1	297	212	229	1	KCNA6 - PIK3R1	376	388	357	160
ADAMTS12 - PIK3R1	179	316	354	173	PID1 - PIK3R1	378	292	360	140

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between PIK3R1 VS Individual members.

P2RY14 / SLCO3A1 / BOK / MYOZ1 / SERTM1 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPP
 / FAM43B / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / PRKD1 / FLRT2 / SHC4 / ANKRD20A5P /
 KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / MME / FAM180B / SPN
 / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 /
 SYT15 / FAM155A / VIT / ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P /
 TENM3 / ITGB2-AS1 / CYP4F29P and SNX18P13.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS PIK3R1											
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T PIK3R1											
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		
ABI3BP - PIK3R1	316	338	355	207	PDE1C - PIK3R1	380	373	387	197		
MMP16 - PIK3R1	289	247	336	102	TSPAN7 - PIK3R1	188	340	310	264		
PPP2R2B - PIK3R1	369	365	254	222	EXTL1 - PIK3R1	315	279	315	195		
S100B - PIK3R1	351	389	374	240	COL26A1 - PIK3R1	390	380	341	214		
VCAM1 - PIK3R1	303	224	337	97	FRZB - PIK3R1	338	336	289	234		
CCDC74A - PIK3R1	197	253	194	364	C1QTNF7 - PIK3R1	365	353	343	149		
APBB2 - PIK3R1	261	127	244	355	HPGD - PIK3R1	210	337	346	340		
F2RL2 - PIK3R1	306	286	371	119	RHOBTB3 - PIK3R1	384	377	366	202		
EBF1 - PIK3R1	345	335	319	85	TMEM200A - PIK3R1	213	251	264	323		
MYOZ3 - PIK3R1	235	370	299	86	SBSPPON - PIK3R1	371	239	317	227		
CA3 - PIK3R1	353	329	352	169	SVEP1 - PIK3R1	352	288	359	170		
HSPA12A - PIK3R1	312	284	295	80	PDZRN4 - PIK3R1	360	351	313	215		
TMEM130 - PIK3R1	392	392	369	176	NNMT - PIK3R1	318	390	386	163		
PRRT2 - PIK3R1	215	271	275	11	VAMP5 - PIK3R1	280	220	227	362		
ENHO - PIK3R1	321	307	293	141	CPT1C - PIK3R1	294	350	367	224		
STK32A - PIK3R1	362	357	388	135	SCG2 - PIK3R1	363	387	392	156		
STARD5 - PIK3R1	358	277	207	65	PEAK1 - PIK3R1	200	210	213	348		
SUSD5 - PIK3R1	295	237	276	190	HOXB2 - PIK3R1	183	234	311	347		
CD248 - PIK3R1	262	294	279	27	DNAH12 - PIK3R1	322	252	205	81		
P2RY14 - PIK3R1	247	246	269	345	SLCO3A1 - PIK3R1	211	305	297	320		
BOK - PIK3R1	284	260	333	387	MYOZ1 - PIK3R1	199	203	286	78		
SERTM1 - PIK3R1	340	386	384	245	PLCB1 - PIK3R1	325	213	232	313		
NTM - PIK3R1	385	289	385	89	RGS6 - PIK3R1	381	375	348	229		
PAPPA - PIK3R1	379	367	373	211	FAM43B - PIK3R1	204	257	238	380		
TMEM119 - PIK3R1	364	331	356	257	OLFML1 - PIK3R1	190	323	335	346		
PRKD1 - PIK3R1	288	362	332	198	FLRT2 - PIK3R1	258	190	361	392		
SHC4 - PIK3R1	350	230	358	259	ANKRD20A5P - PIK3R1	391	378	378	231		
KBTBD12 - PIK3R1	148	287	260	389	LDLRAD2 - PIK3R1	313	290	370	68		
PLAC9 - PIK3R1	181	310	340	146	NUGGC - PIK3R1	329	349	226	272		
FAM180A - PIK3R1	357	372	391	220	MME - PIK3R1	375	382	389	187		
FAM180B - PIK3R1	389	376	382	209	SPN - PIK3R1	301	343	241	130		
CLEC9A - PIK3R1	339	262	328	280	DLGAP2 - PIK3R1	346	348	344	218		
MMP17 - PIK3R1	202	347	204	248	DLL1 - PIK3R1	212	313	212	25		
ZNF521 - PIK3R1	355	315	282	263	RYR3 - PIK3R1	285	325	351	164		
RHOT1P2 - PIK3R1	370	371	390	167	PLPP4 - PIK3R1	331	369	350	199		
SYT15 - PIK3R1	222	123	363	376	FAM155A - PIK3R1	341	266	284	82		
VIT - PIK3R1	388	391	379	208	ANKRD20A9P - PIK3R1	383	384	376	212		
GPX3 - PIK3R1	382	300	349	147	HMGB3P7 - PIK3R1	195	217	365	96		
ANKRD20A11P - PIK3R1	336	385	362	268	TENM3 - PIK3R1	342	379	372	181		
ITGB2-AS1 - PIK3R1	304	302	277	28	CYP4F29P - PIK3R1	368	368	377	200		
SNX18P13 - PIK3R1	366	374	271	244							

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between PIK3R1 VS Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic PIK3R1 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of PIK3R1-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t PIK3R1

SEMA3F / CD38 / CD4 / ALOX5 / CD74 / APBA2 ...
COL11A1 / PRDM6 / TSPAN32 / ITGB5 / SLC23A2 ...
PCSK5 / NFATC4 / CD40 / RIMS4 / MXRA5 / PCSK1N ...
CCL22 / CORO2B / PDGFRL / PCOLCE / ENG / CDH23 ...
CHRNE / CNTNAP1 / COL1A1 / PMP22 / TRIM2 / CRYAB ...
SLC35F2 / SASH1 / VNN1 / GHR / CDH6 / PARD3B / WLS ...
OLFML3 / IGSF21 / PTCH2 / NRP2 / C1orf198 / PHF19 ...
PLXDC2 / CRISPLD1 / PLAU / BHLHE41 / SGCE / FCHO1 ...
PXDN / LILRB2 / MYH10 / LRCH1 / LCP1 / ALPK3 / ENPP2 ...
SYTL2 / EMILIN1 / CBLN3 / FBLN5 / IGFBP4 / NLRP12 ...
C1orf162 / RBMS3 / FAM198A / CTDSPL / MYH15 / BOC ...
FAM105A / SPATA9 / TRIM7 / DAAM2 / CHRNB3 / NTRK2 ...
DRD2 / FEZ1 / MKX / PRSS23 / KCNA6 / ADAMTS12 / PID1 ...
ABI3BP / PDE1C / MMP16 / TSPAN7 / PPP2R2B / EXTL1 ...
S100B / COL26A1 / VCAM1 / FRZB / CCDC74A / C1QTNF7 ...
APBB2 / HPGD / F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 / EBF1 / TMEM200A ...
MYOZ3 / SBSPON / CA3 / SVEP1 / HSPA12A / PDZRN4 ...
TMEM130 / NNMT / PRRT2 / VAMP5 / ENHO / CPT1C ...
STK32A / SCG2 / STARD5 / PEAK1 / SUSD5 / HOXB2 ...
CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / SLCO3A1 / BOK / MYOZ1 ...
SERTM1 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPP / FAM43B / TMEM119 ...
OLFML1 / PRKD1 / FLRT2 / SHC4 / ANKRD20A5P / KBTBD12 ...
LDLRAD2 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / MME / FAM180B / SPN ...
CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / RHOT1P2 ...
PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A / VIT / ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 ...
ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / ITGB2-AS1 / CYP4F29P / SNX18P13 PIK3R1

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PIK3R1 and Individual members.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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